

NATURE, SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT AND THEIR SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPLICATIONS IN HUMAN LIFE

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Annotation: Today, the fact that humanity lives a stable life remains due to a huge number of natural and Human Factors. In particular, the increased antropogenic effect on nature, the actions that a person does to meet his needs, are the cause of global problems. We are still unable to fully feel that it is too late than ever that the objective laws of nature are superior to subjective laws, and that this realization is bowing in the face of our feelings that can drag us into the arms of many disasters and disasters. And in this article we want to comment on this and its history, albeit briefly.

Key words: Nature, humanity, historical progress, Central Asian

It is known that many events that occurred in nature – earth tremors, kisses, dives and surges, floods, floods, heavy rains and torrential rains of varying degrees, floods, storms, frosty winters and scorching summers, volcanic eruptions, fires and the spread of various infectious diseases-brought severe consequences to humans, fauna and flora. In particular, many examples of material culture, the city-it caused the destruction of villages, the crisis of various civilizations, the premature passage of millions of people through the world.

The efforts of mankind to prevent and reduce the negative consequences of various phenomena occurring in nature in order to ensure their own safety at first gave rise to various religious views, and later to scientific approaches. In particular, the fear that the whole life of primitive people was dependent on the whims of nature and its helplessness in the fight against them, as well as from the stichian phenomena of nature, which have become a constant companion in consequence, initially led to the origin of religious views ¹.

Therefore, in the history of ancient peoples, many objects and phenomena that exist in nature, such as The Sun, Moon, Water, storm, wind, are named after the gods. In particular, there was an early religious view – in animism, people believed in the existence of soul and soul in the environment that surrounds them. Phenomena such as the alternation of seasons, storms, thunderstorms, the occurrence of strong hurricanes are embodied by the spirit natural phenomena,² those who understand and worship him. For example, the Romans were the God Of Heaven, Thunder and lightning-Jupiter, the God of the sea-Neptune, the God of the Moon - Diana, the God Of Fire and blacksmiths-volcano, the God of spring and love-Venus³, and deb Egyptians - the God Of The Sun-Amon-ra, the God of the Nile-Hapi, the God of the

¹ Жўраев У., Саиджонов Й.. Дунё динлари тарихи, -Тошкент., “Шарқ”, 1998 , - Б. 21

² Крушкол Ю.С. таҳр. ост. Қадимги дунё тарихи, -Тошкент: Ўқитувчи, 1975, - Б.144

³ Крушкол Ю.С. таҳр. ост. Қадимги дунё тарихи, -Тошкент: Ўқитувчи, 1975, - Б. 144

kingdom of erosti-Osiris, the God of bad luck, desert and storm - set, the God of wisdom and medicine tot - Moon,⁴ as they saw it, the Greeks considered Zeus their greatness, and others⁵.

In the history of all peoples, the shining of The Sun and the moon at night indicate that the year is coming well, there are no various natural disasters, people live a peaceful, peaceful life. That is why they saw the Gods Of The Sun and Moon as gods of goodness, wisdom, beauty. Even temples have been built in Egypt in honor of The Sun God⁶.

Protection from natural phenomena as a result of historical progress, as well as the fight against its consequences, the possibility of major changes in the life of mankind, the formation of specific values,⁷

the reason for the emergence of scientific views. In particular, people were forced to come up with clothes, build housing. As a result, human life improved and became more civilized.

However, sources regarding the coverage of the history of mankind pay little attention to the history of the influence of natural phenomena. Of course, while special government agencies were not established in those periods to prevent, eliminate the consequences of emergency incidents, such tasks were assigned to other state agencies.

However, the occurrence of natural phenomena has caused enormous losses in the human past. Mosius testified that the fruit of human thought was the culture of the ancient world, 4 of the seven wonderful wonders of the world turned into ruins as a result of emergencies of a different nature⁸. For example, in miles. AV. In Semirami, built in the 6th century by the decree of the Babylonian ruler Nebuchadnezzar, the Hanging Gardens were destroyed by flooding. The tsunami caused by a powerful earthquake in the Eastern Mediterranean on July 21, 365 AD, destroyed the Alexandria lighthouse in Egypt and caused the death of 5,000 people in Alexandria itself⁹.

However, while Disaster Management is found in the history of many peoples, in the past of our country, information about natural disasters and their prevention is also contained in the Zoroastrian Bible, "Avesto". The book does not seem to have lost much of its relevance even now, with the ideas put forward in the book on the Prevention of natural phenomena.

The book explained the process of struggle between the God of goodness, Ahura Mazda, the God of death and evil, Ahriman, in connection with the phenomena of nature. In the fifth fargard of "Avesto", water, flood, and fire are said: "...Water does not kill anyone. He is tan zavoli, the death devi Astuvayazut, who pulls kimsa into his domain and tightens his limbs. Then the cellob pushes it into its depths and into the expanses of water"¹⁰.

Zoroastrian religion shows a very careful treatment of water, soil, Fire, Mountain, and glaciers and fauna, which are factors of human survival. Even anyone who violated the rules of preserving water, fire, ground and air was punished with beatings. Keeping them pure was considered an important factor in human survival.

⁴ Ўша жойда, - Б.144

⁵ Авдиев В. И. Қадимги дунё тарихи, -Тошкент: Шарқ, 1975., - Б. 159

⁶ Асқар Маҳкам таржимаси "Авесто" тарихий-адабий ёдгорлик, -Тошкент: Шарқ, 2001, - Б. 123

⁷ Назаров Қ, Аксиология қадриятлар фалсафаси, -Тошкент: Маънавият, 1998., - Б. 65

⁸ Болалар энциклопедияси "У ким, бу нима" , -Тошкент, Ўқитувчи, 1987, - Б. 221-222.

⁹ Илёсова З. Цунами // Мухофаза +, 2005,- № 01, - Б. 25.

¹⁰ Илёсова З. Цунами // Мухофаза +, 2005,- № 01, - Б. 67.

Islam, which entered after Zoroastrianism, also occupies an important place in the life of the peoples of Central Asia. In both religions that our people believe, qualities such as purity, purity, purity and moderation are glorified. In particular, in verse 49 of the Qamar Surah of the Quran, the Holy Book of Islam: "of course, we solved everything by Measure",¹¹ is called. In other words, everything in the world: water, soil, air, animal, nabotot are also created by God in a way that is interconnected by a certain measure. If this balance is slightly disturbed, many problems can arise for humanity¹².

In a number of verses of the Qur'an Karim, information is given about the punishment of the people through natural phenomena. In the Islamic world, the Qur'an is a post-Karim book, The "Al-Jomi'as-sahih" of Imam Ismail al - Bukhari-a hadith collection also mentions that heavy rains brought great tribulations.

In addition, it is found in historical sources. In particular, the first information about the earthquake on the territory of our country is found in Abu Said Gardizi's book Zaynal Akhbor. It states: "in 224 (838-839), as a result of a powerful earthquake in Fergana, many buildings were destroyed". Muarrix Juvaini of Khorasan's "history of Jahangir Genghis Khan" records that the 1208 Khwarezm earthquake destroyed many buildings and killed 2,000 people, even when part of Urganch fell into the Amudarya and the city fell into ruins¹³.

Such information is provided by the historian scholar H.Sadiqov's "Security Service in the Kingdom of Amir Temur",¹⁴ Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur " Baburnoma,¹⁵ Muhammad Tohir ibn Abdul Qasim's "amazing tabokot",¹⁶ in the work, in the manuscript of "Gulshan al-mulk" by Muhammad Jacob ibn Muhammad Daniel, N.V.Hanikov's work on the Khanate of Bukhara,¹⁷ it is also found in .

This can also be seen in the example of the Tashkent earthquake of April 26, 1966, which has so far been sealed in the minds of people with its severe consequences.

It can be said that the more ancient the phenomena of nature are and have a specific power of influence on human life, the more ancient it is to try to know its secrets and apply measures to protect against them. For example, Greek scholars who lived in history before BC Pythagoras,¹⁸

Strabo, Democritus, Aristotle, and others attempted a scientific approach to the study of the causes of earthquakes. In our country, however, the opinion of Abu Rayhan Beruniy and Abu Ali ibn Sina about the main causes of earthquakes has found scientific proof as far back as the 20th century. In particular, Abu Raihon Beruni's " India", his views on how natural disasters affect changes in social relations have not lost their relevance today.

In history, protection from natural phenomena, which have a different appearance in the life of the peoples of the world, has also played a key role in the formation of certain traditions and values¹⁹. The Masters, on the other hand, used techniques to improve Castle strength in

¹¹ Муҳаммад Содиқ Муҳаммад Юсуф таржимаси Қуръони Карим -Тошкент: Шарқ, 2009, - Б.531.

¹² Иброҳимов А. Руҳий озиқ маҳзани, -Тошкент: Янги аср авлоди, 2009, - Б. 161-162.

¹³ Иброҳимов Р. Солномалар ҳикояси //Фуқаро муҳофазаси,-2002, -№1, - Б.28.

¹⁴ Содиқов Ҳ. Амир Темур салтанатида хавфсизлик хизмати, -Тошкент: ART FLEX, 1916, -Б. 379.

¹⁵ Халқаро Бобур Фонди. Бобурнома, -Тошкент: Ўқитувчи, 2008, -Б 124.

¹⁶ Иброҳимов Р. Солномалар ҳикояси //Фуқаро муҳофазаси, 2002, -№1, - Б.28.

¹⁷ Ўша жойда,- Б.28.

²⁶ Ўша жойда, - Б. 18.

¹⁹ Норбоев А., Қодирова Ф. Қадриятлар негизи // "Маърифат" газетаси, 2010, 30 октябрь, №40

the construction of the cinchli houses and to prevent the ground from breaking during shaking. Such houses have withstood earthquakes that occur both horizontally and vertically²⁰ and it was used for a long time.

As you know, Uzbekistan ranks at the forefront among the countries of the world with its cultural monuments. It can be said that both the seismic active zone of these buildings and the area where drastic climatic changes take place have been raging for many centuries, and the main reason for serving the benefit of our people and our country today is that our architects were able to skillfully use local objects: soil, stone, cane, ganj, paint, water and fire.

As a result of these realities that occurred in the 20th century, nature came under enormous anthropogenic pressure. The new techniques and technologies created were first turned not into social spheres, but into military ones. That is, it led to the emergence of weapons of mass destruction against humanity. Realizing that mistakes made during the Times of their manufacture, testing, storage, transportation and use would have dire consequences, attempts were made to increase it, to be numerically superior.

Another of the peculiarities of this period is that in order to get the young independent states that have just been developing into their own influence, both systems have tried to use the more extensive method in economic development. This caused the deterioration of soil, air and water composition to take on a global appearance.

As a result, according to the UN, those who suffered from emergency situations in the 60s of the 20th century made up 1.6% of the population of the Earth, by the 1980s it had increased by 3.5 %²¹. In the last quarter of this century, 3.5 million of natural disasters were lost. the man died, 3 billion. more than one person was injured²². In the last years of the last century, the number of people who died as a result of various disasters grew by 6% per year²³. Or, according to the data of the scientific research center for disasters in Brussels, in the next three decades, 14 million from natural disasters worldwide. kishi is deceased. The total economic loss was 400 crore. US dollars. If in the 60-70s of the last century, an average of 62 people were injured from emergencies of a different natural and man-made Nature, today it is one person out of every 55²⁴.

At the 2015 third international conference on the reduction of the risk of natural disasters in senday, Japan, during the period 2005-2015, natural disasters killed 700 thousand people, 1.5 billion. to the victim of a person,1.4 billion. it was recognized that it caused the injury of a person. Again, at this conference, it was noted that natural disasters caused US \$ 1.3 trillion in damage to the economy of world countries, as well as natural disasters in 2008-2012, which led to the displacement of 144 million people²⁵.

This UN Conference and the activities adopted in it showed that the Prevention of various natural disasters and the increase of protection measures against them is one of the

²⁰ Ўша жойда, 2010, 30 октябрь, № 40

²¹ Кол.автор. Защита населения и территорий от чрезвычайных ситуация, -Тошкент: ГЗИ, 2003. -С. 9.

²² Ўша жойда, -С.11.

²³ Ўша жойда, - С. 11.

²⁴ Сергеев И., Предупреждени чрезвычайных ситуаций как один элементов экологической безопасности //“Экологическая безопасность и гражданская инциатива”, 2005, №6, -С. 9.

²⁵ Протоколы Третья всемирная конференция ООН по снижению риска бедствий. Сендай-Япония. 2015, –С. 15-16.

important things facing the world States. Prior to this period, the formation of structures associated with the IAEA, the World Health Organization and the preservation of the environment under the UN, the adoption of various programs, as well as the international adoption of certain days are also evidence of this. In particular, this can be seen in the example of the annual date of October 13, the so-called "International Day for the Prevention of natural disasters", April 22, the so-called "Earth Day", as well as events taking place internationally.

At present, the formation of special state bodies and systems on the issue of the Prevention of disasters and disasters of different types in the countries of the world can be viewed as a period of increased attention and practical action on the further development of their work in cooperation with each other and with prestigious international organizations.

One of the most important features of this period is the fact that it is recognized by man that emergencies of different tones are a great danger to the sustainable development of mankind, and the fact that anthropogenic factors are the main reason for it is recognized by states.

Important features of this period can be seen in the following cases:

the direction of emergency response of states, political forces, international organizations and national public organizations began to become the basis of the type of activity;

in addition to the formation of special offices in states to prevent emergency situations, international prestigious organizations in the field have also emerged;

non-profit emergency organizations were also formed in the states and their activities became legal.

That being said, humanity has in its history tried to prevent disasters and disasters of different nature, as well as reduce and eliminate the consequences when they occur. These actions have led to the formation, development, and further improvement of personality culture.

Even today, the rapid development of any society - the human mind-is measured by its thinking, science and the techniques and technologies it creates. But his thought has not yet fully realized the negative consequences that the result of the progress being made.

The various economic crises and financial recessions taking place in the world over the next ten years are also explained by the increasing anthropogenic influence on nature. In particular, looking at the data of the UN World Food Program, the price of food in the world in 2011 was 25% more expensive. It is estimated that the main factor contributing to this is the economy and the environmental environment. Over the past 40 years, as a result of the use of anthropogenic technologies in the cultivation of agricultural products, about a third of the world's fertile land has fallen into disrepair.

Another factor is the increase in industrial production and urbanization rates in urban areas leading to a decrease in water consumption for agricultural products.²⁶

This also has a strong impact on the relations between states using transboundary rivers. In particular, the arid arrival of some years is causing food depletion as well as food prices around the world, increasing the risk of food shortages, as well as increased desertification and the occurrence of environmental disasters.

²⁶ Абдулбоқиев Ф., Бирни кўриб фикр қил // "XXI АСР" - 2012, 19 апрель. 16-(440)- сон

In place of the conclusion, it can be said that natural phenomena have always played an important role in the life of a person. These events have been called disasters and disasters of various manifestations, the damage they caused to humanity, the negative effects on the health and life of people. For this reason, man has long been trying to prevent these effects, to reduce their suffering. In a certain sense, it also caused the civilization of the human world, the growth of Science and enlightenment.

Natural, man-made and ecological disasters and disasters are a process that is characteristic of each era, and the increase in the impact of humanity on nature has also led to an increase in such risks. Especially these risks can be clearly seen in the next 100 years.

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